

РАЗДЕЛ. ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS
FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTEGRATED SCIENTIFIC
AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT**

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Annotation: The issues of formation of mechanisms for the implementation of integrated scientific and technical research and development attract the attention of not only scientists, but also business representatives, which is associated with an understanding of the importance of the innovations impact and scientific achievements on socio-economic development through structural changes in the knowledge economy. Despite the existing research, this scientific problem requires a more detailed study, since it is of particular importance in the context of the development of the digital economy, in which knowledge and information are the main resources that affect competitive advantages. A comparative analysis of the mechanisms for the implementation of complex scientific and technical research and development has been carried out. Methods and tools for assessing the innovative and scientific and technical potential of integrated research and development are proposed.

Keywords: knowledge economy, digitalization, socio-economic development, scientific research, innovation

ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНЫХ НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ И РАЗРАБОТОК

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Аннотация: Вопросы формирования механизмов реализации комплексных научно-технических исследований и разработок привлекают внимание не только ученых, но и представителей бизнеса, что связано с пониманием важности воздействия инноваций и научных достижений на общество. -экономическое развитие через структурные изменения в экономике знаний. Несмотря на имеющиеся исследования, данная научная проблема требует более детального изучения, поскольку приобретает особое значение в условиях развития цифровой экономики, в которой знания и информация являются основными ресурсами, влияющими на конкурентные преимущества. Проведен сравнительный анализ механизмов реализации комплексных научно-технических исследований и разработок. Предложены методы и инструменты оценки инновационного и научно-технического потенциала комплексных исследований и разработок.

Ключевые слова: экономика знаний, цифровизация, социально-экономическое развитие, научные исследования, инновации

Such an important concept as interdisciplinary research is not an abstraction. Within the framework of complex scientific research and development, materials scientists, physicists, chemists, biologists, pharmacists, etc. closely cooperate. Currently, despite the fact that scientists have their own fundamental areas of scientific research, much attention is also paid to the

implementation of interdisciplinary projects [1, 2]. For example, one of the promising areas related to wastewater treatment is developing at the intersection of chemistry, biology, physics and medicine. Without a combination of efforts of specialists from each of these industries, innovative results will never be competitive [3, 4].

The basis of complex targeted scientific and technical research is the creation of an integral system for the development and testing of innovative products. Complex projects prove their high efficiency, even after the completion of which the established links between scientists continue to operate, which is successfully used for scientific research, and not only for the search for new technologies.

World experience unequivocally demonstrates that without close cooperation between scientists of different directions, the development of modern science is impossible [5, 6]. The pure sciences have practically no chance of getting more or less serious support from state institutions. Whether such an approach is correct, whether it harms fundamental research is a rather debatable question, but it is complex scientific and technical research and development that find their practical application faster.

In foreign scientific institutions there are no classical faculties built according to the principle of correspondence to one science [7, 8]. There are no classical departments with a narrow specialization. Scientific groups are formed, usually headed by a well-known professor, with a very flexible structure and freedom to choose scientific directions. Well-known universities, of course, also have classical divisions, but the goals and objectives of each of them clearly spell out the need not only to carry out their own research, but also to closely cooperate with other sciences [9, 10].

It is difficult to imagine the sustainable development of the scientific and innovation sphere, and, accordingly, the knowledge economy, without the possibility of using such an effective tool as targeted complex scientific and technical projects, which can be carried out by leading centers, providing work based on modern information technologies [11, 12].

In modern conditions of dynamic development of information technologies and the digital economy, innovation and science are the key to building a competitive economy and ensuring sustainable development. Focusing on labor-intensive and material-intensive industrial production becomes an obstacle to ensuring high competitive economic development and the development of human capital, which in the conditions of the knowledge

economy becomes a key asset capable of creating added value based on the production and use of knowledge in all spheres of social and economic life [13, 14].

It is the rapid development of innovations that is a determinant that changes the structure of the economy, entails the emergence of new industries, their automation, the development and use of artificial intelligence.

The issues of the formation and implementation of innovation policy attract the attention of not only scientists, but also business representatives and politicians, which is associated with an understanding of the importance of the impact of innovations and scientific achievements on socio-economic development through structural changes both in the economy and in society, changes in the chain creating value from suppliers to end users. The development of scientific, technical and innovation policy includes the development of individual subsystems and mechanisms of the socio-economic and political system of the country, key guidelines, plans and strategies for the development of the knowledge economy.

Any country should clearly develop high-quality, flexible political instruments in the field of innovation and science in general, capable of ensuring the achievement of high competitive positions of the state in the world market and including international ratings.

The study of trends in innovative development and human capital made it possible to identify the key problems of the reduction of highly qualified scientific personnel, an analysis of the existing forecasts for the evolution of the human resources potential of domestic science, necessary for the implementation of complex scientific and technical research and development, was carried out. Despite the existing research, this scientific problem requires a more detailed study, since it is of particular importance in the context of the development of the digital economy, in which knowledge and information are the main resources that affect obtaining competitive advantages.

At present, many problems have accumulated that have not been resolved for a long time and have led to the stagnation of the national innovation system, a significant reduction in the number of scientists due to the low level of material support and migration, the closure of scientific schools, and the decline in the material and technical base of research institutions due to restructuring. The rating of exports of high-tech products confirms the conclusions made. High-tech products include aerospace, computer and office

machines, electronics-telecommunications, pharmaceutical products, scientific instruments, electrical equipment/machinery, chemical products and non-electrical equipment/machinery.

Positive growth trends persist in those industries that use extensive factors of production and do not require a high level of innovative activity, as they are based on the export of raw materials or products of low production stages, as a result, the low level of competitiveness of the economy and the country's lag in socio-economic and innovative-investment development.

There is a loss of connection between scientific results and their implementation in production. Among the reasons for this situation, one can single out a significant reduction in funding for science, a drop in the prestige of scientific work in society, significant emigration of promising highly qualified scientists due to insufficient material incentives, physical and moral depreciation of the scientific and technical base, lack of an innovative development strategy, support and understanding from the government, imperfection of legal regulation of the implementation of complex scientific and technical research and innovative developments.

Innovative activity as a form of investment includes: production and distribution of fundamentally new equipment and technologies; progressive intersectional structural shifts; implementation of long-term scientific and technical projects; funding for fundamental research to ensure qualitative changes in production facilities; development and implementation of new resource-saving technologies designed to improve the social and environmental state of production [15, 16].

Organizational and economic mechanisms for the implementation of complex scientific and technical research and development should include: involvement of interdisciplinary specialists in decision-making processes in the field of science and education; creation of an interdepartmental council for the development of science and technology, the main task of which is to provide proposals for determining scientific priorities.

State institutions should apply financial-credit and tax instruments to create favorable economic conditions for the introduction of scientific and scientific-technical activities and ensure an increase in the volume of funding for science from all sources.

For a better understanding of the situation in terms of the state and assessment of the innovative, scientific and technical potential of integrated scientific and technical research and development, groups of criteria have been

developed: an innovative leader, an active innovator, a moderate innovator, and an emerging innovator.

A comparative analysis of the mechanisms for the implementation of complex scientific and technical research and development has been carried out. Currently, domestic approaches are significantly inferior in terms of the main indicators that form the composite efficiency index. The highest indicator is noted for the human capital group, which indicates a strong personnel component, while low values for the research systems and financial support group indicate an unfavorable environment for the functioning of human resources.

The existing implementation mechanisms can be attributed to the moderate innovator group, however, many indicators are consistently in the emerging innovator group. The low value of the indicator of entrepreneurial activity indicates a low level of innovative cooperation between small and medium-sized businesses with subjects of research and innovation, a low level of support for start-ups, a low level of co-financing of state research projects, etc. There is a low level of innovation and entrepreneurial orientation, the lack of state support for innovative, scientific and technical activities and favorable conditions for its results.

The number of scientific workers is of great importance for ensuring scientific, technical and innovative development. The stagnation of science and the decrease in the prestige of scientific work are evidenced by data on the number of performers of scientific research and development and researchers per thousand people of the employed population.

Among the main reasons for the reduction of highly qualified scientific personnel, one can single out low wages, a decrease in the prestige of scientific work in society, a low level of scientific and technical base and funding for research and development, poor performance of social elevators for young scientists and negative expectations of a further decline in the scientific sphere.

Scientific and methodological approaches to forecasting the development of complex scientific and technical research and development have been developed, which made it possible to calculate the further evolution of the human resources potential of domestic science for the next decades. According to studies, it was predicted that if the existing trends in the reduction in the number of researchers continue, then in ten years their number will be more than halved, and this, in turn, will lead to a decrease in the country's

innovative capabilities, innovative development and further loss of competitiveness.

A number of measures are proposed to bring domestic indicators of science staffing closer to international standards, in particular, every five years it is necessary to ensure at least a doubling of the number of young people entering science, while avoiding annual losses. Consequently, if urgent measures are implemented, the predicted value of the number of young researchers will increase significantly.

Based on the conducted research, it can be concluded that it is urgent to ensure the implementation of extraordinary measures to support science in order to ensure its revival, and not survival. And this means the development and implementation of an innovative development strategy, the improvement of the existing regulatory framework, the introduction of financial and tax-credit instruments for financing the scientific sphere. A striking example of the implementation of relevant measures are India and China, which go to extraordinary measures and expenses in order to obtain the status of an economic leader in the world. For example, China spends huge amounts of money on returning scientists from abroad, lures away foreign scientists and students, and the salary of scientists over the past ten years has grown twenty-fold, and India has built a whole city for researchers and developers of information technologies. Such examples testify to a clear understanding by countries of the importance of science in a promising and highly competitive future [17, 18].

In addition, it is necessary to use the experience of the world's leading countries in the field of legal regulation of innovation activities and develop their own model of innovation policy, which will become the basis for improving legal regulation in the implementation of integrated scientific and technical research and development [19, 20]. In particular, it is necessary to provide incentives for the production of innovative products by enterprises through the use of tax incentives for enterprises engaged in the creation of innovative products, the provision of interest-free loans, compensation, to stimulate the development of research and technological cooperation within the framework of public-private partnership, to stimulate the development of cooperation between enterprises in various industries among themselves with the participation of scientific institutions, the development of small and medium-sized innovative businesses.

Prospects for further research should be noted in the context of developing proposals and measures to enhance innovation, using foreign experience in supporting scientific personnel. It must be understood that the development of science and innovation depends on the state scientific and technological policy, as well as on measures to support entrepreneurship, especially the creation of favorable conditions implementation of complex scientific and technical research and development for the development of innovative entrepreneurship, which in turn can ensure the stability of economic development, a high level of competitiveness in the world market and the ability to respond in time to the challenges of a new technological order.

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